

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEED ABILITIES IN ROWERS**Mambetnazarova Aynura Orinbaevna****Nukus School of Higher Sports Mastery in Olympic and National
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ABSTRACT

Rowing as a sport requires from an athlete not only strength and endurance but also a high level of speed abilities. This thesis scientifically substantiates the main factors, training methods, and step-by-step approaches to developing speed qualities in athletes engaged in rowing.

Speed ability in rowing is the athlete's ability to achieve the maximum frequency of strikes in a short time, increase the speed of movement in the water, and achieve superiority at the starting stage. Speed qualities are of decisive importance, especially for athletes competing in short distances (200-500 meters).

Speed ability is largely related to the neuromuscular system, reaction speed, coordination of movements, and strength qualities. When developing speed in rowers, attention is paid to the following main directions:

1. General speed-forming exercises:

running short distances (30-60 meters) at maximum speed; plummometric exercises (jumps, quick lifting and lowering of a barbell, exercises "burpee," "box jump");

Exercises that increase motor reactions (reactions to signals, exercises for starting quick movements).

2. Special speed exercises:

Short-term (15-30 seconds) maximum speed rowing exercises on a rowing ergometer; interval training in water - fast rowing at 100-250 meters with 1-2 minute rest intervals; "Start speed" exercises - moving at maximum speed over short distances at the start of the competition.

3. Speed-supporting endurance exercises:

Training with medium-intensity loads at distances of 500-1000 meters; exercises that develop anaerobic muscle capabilities to maintain speed without losing it.

4. Technical training:

Improving technology also plays a significant role in increasing speed. The amplitude of each stroke, the angle of entry into the water, the body movement, and the coordination of the limbs must be performed with precision. Technical errors reduce speed and increase energy consumption. Therefore, coaches can effectively develop speed qualities by conducting video

analysis of athletes' movements, studying biomechanical indicators, and eliminating technical errors.

5. Physiological preparation:

In the development of speed qualities, the activity of the neuromuscular system, the speed of muscle fiber contraction, and the state of the cardiovascular system are of great importance. Therefore, during training, the intensity of the load is gradually increased, and the recovery periods must be sufficient. Excessive loads lead to muscle fatigue and a decrease in speed.

Studies show that in the system of long-term training in increasing speed, phasing, an individual approach, and variability in training are important factors. In the early stages of training, emphasis is placed on general physical preparedness, and later, special speed exercises and the rhythm of working in the water are developed.

Conclusion

The effectiveness of the development of speed abilities of rowers is determined by scientific planning of the training process, the correct selection of load intensity, and taking into account individual characteristics. Regular development of speed improves the athlete's starting advantage, rhythm of strikes, and overall result in competition.

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